

Case study in digital humanities: Roman inscriptions in Serbia

Dragana Nikolić

Institute for Balkan Studies of SASA, Belgrade, Serbia

ddgrbic@gmail.com

Abstract

The aim of the paper is to present the project of the Institute for Balkan Studies of the Serbian Academy of Sciences and Arts (SASA) "EpiDOc XML Encoding of Roman Inscriptions from Serbia: Digitization of Ancient Epigraphic Heritage". The project focuses on research, training, digital documenting, and digital edition of Roman inscriptions from the territory of Serbia (the Roman province of Upper Moesia and parts of Lower Pannonia, Dalmatia, and Thrace), aiming to form a national e-archive of inscriptions encoded in EpiDoc TEI-XML format. This collection of digital corpora will represent a completely new epigraphic edition that is furthermore born-digital, freely accessible, and ready for interchange. The project mission is to educate, inspire, and instigate collaborative work and new concepts in epigraphic research. It is envisioned as a core for networking and intensifying the collaboration between research and cultural institutions.

Keywords: Roman inscriptions; Digital epigraphy; EpiDoc XML; Digital humanities.